

A Novel Infimum Dimension Nash Embedding for 3D Projective Shape Data

Robert L. Paige* Vic Patrangenaru† Mihaela Pricop-Jeckstadt‡

Abstract

An isometric embedding of a Riemannian manifold in an Euclidean space is an embedding such that the Riemannian structure on each tangent space is induced by the scalar product in the ambient space; such an embedding preserves path lengths, angles, areas and volumes. Such a mapping preserves much of the geometric information contained in the original Riemannian manifold where the data is valued allowing for some computationally advantages. In addition if the Riemannian manifold is homogeneous then we would also want the such an embedding, to be equivariant. The Veronese-Whitney (VW) embedding is an isometric equivariant embedding for 3D projective shape data. It is in fact the only embedding used in the analysis of 3D projective shape data, at the present time. In this paper we consider a novel equivariant isometric embedding, the Nash embedding into a Euclidean space of a lower dimension than the Euclidean space where the Veronese-Whitney embedding is valued. We compare the performance of the novel Nash embedding-based statistical techniques with those based on the VW embedding in Monte Carlo studies and a real data example.

Key Words: Extrinsic shape analysis, Nash embedding, Nonparametric test, Three-dimensional projective shape analysis

1. Introduction

An embedding of an object Z in object W involves a one-to-one structure-preserving map from Z into W (e.g. the circle embedded in two-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^2). An isometric embedding is often considered since it preserves path lengths, angles, areas and volumes, hence much of the geometry of the object being embedded. With regards to data science applications, vector embeddings provide easy access to classical statistical techniques; see for instance Kukreja et al. (2023). Furthermore, it is of interest to determine the vector embedding with the smallest possible dimension.

Three-dimensional (3D) digital image data is becoming increasingly more common in science and technology. This is particularly so in areas such as computer vision, medicine, dentistry, manufacturing, architecture and archaeology. A point in 3D projective space, denoted as $\mathbb{R}P^3$, is often obtained from two uncalibrated 2D digital camera images of the same point. In fact, this is the mathematics underlying binocular vision; see Hartley et al. (1992).

$\mathbb{R}P^3$ is also a Riemannian manifold and can be thought of as the collection of all axes passing through the origin in \mathbb{R}^4 or equivalently as \mathbb{S}^3 with the antipodal points identified, the Riemannian structure is inherited from the Riemannian structure of \mathbb{S}^3 , since the antipodal map of the sphere is an isometry.

With points in $\mathbb{R}P^3$ denoted as $[x]$, the classical Veronese-Whitney (VW) embedding (Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005)) given as

$$j([x]) = xx^T \text{ where } x^T x = 1$$

and $[x]$ is the projective point corresponding to x so that it embeds $\mathbb{R}P^3$ into $Sym(4, \mathbb{R})$ while being equivariant under orthogonal group $O(4)$ acting on \mathbb{R}^4 but is not isometric

*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Missouri S&T, Rolla, MO 65401

†Department of Statistics, Florida State University, Tallahassee, FL 32306

‡Department of Applied Mathematics, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

with respect to the Frobenius (Euclidean) norm for matrices. However, the fact that the VW embedding is not a vector embedding is more germane to our discussion.

The Nash Theorem (Nash 1956) guarantees the existence of isometric vector embeddings for Riemannian manifolds. Determining such embeddings in closed-form is often at best very challenging but more often not possible. In this work we develop a closed-form isometric (Nash) vector embedding for the projective shape of 3D digital image data that lies in $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^q$ and illustrate a few of its uses in 3D projective shape analysis.

2. Spectral Embeddings for Projective Spaces

Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) developed a closed-form isometric vector embeddings for one and two-dimensional projective shape analysis involving points in $(\mathbb{R}P^1)^q$ and $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$, respectively. Furthermore, the embedding in the present work and the ones in Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) are based on the eigenfunctions of the Laplace-Beltrami operator Δ and hence are examples of spectral embeddings. For a compact, connected and orientable Riemannian manifold \mathcal{M} in terms of coordinate system

$$x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p),$$

that is constructed by chart (U, c) , Δ has the form

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|g(x)|}} \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(g(x)^{ij} \sqrt{|g(x)|} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \right)$$

where $g(x)$, the local representative of the Riemannian structure, is a $p \times p$ positive definite symmetric matrix for all $c^{-1}(x) \in \mathcal{M}$ which has continuous derivatives of all orders and $g(x)^{ij}$ denotes the inverse of $g_{ij}(x)$.

The eigenfunctions of Δ form a complete orthonormal basis

$$\{\varphi_j(x) \text{ for } j = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$$

for $L_2(\mathcal{M})$, the space of square integrable functions on \mathcal{M} where by convention $\varphi_0(x) = 1$; see section 3.3 of Patrangenaru and Ellingson (2015).

Since $\mathbb{R}P^3$ can be identified almost surely with the upper hemisphere of \mathbb{S}^3 , an orthonormal basis for $L_2(\mathbb{R}P^3)$ can be derived from the orthonormal basis for $L_2(\mathbb{S}^3)$; see Tirao and Zurrián (2014) and Hendriks (1990).

3. Nash Embeddings for $\mathbb{R}P^s$ for $s = 1, 2$ and 3

Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) derive the infimum dimension Nash Embeddings for $\mathbb{R}P^1$ and $\mathbb{R}P^2$ as

$$\iota_{\mathbb{R}P^1}([x]) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 x_2 \\ \frac{1}{2} (x_1^2 - x_2^2) \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\iota_{\mathbb{R}P^2}([x]) = \begin{bmatrix} \iota_{\mathbb{R}P^1}([x]) \\ x_1 x_3 \\ x_2 x_3 \\ \frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}} (3x_3^2 - 1) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using the approach outlined in Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) it can be shown that the infimum dimension Nash Embeddings for $\mathbb{R}P^3$ is given as

$$\iota_{\mathbb{R}P^3}([x]) = \begin{bmatrix} \iota_{\mathbb{R}P^2}([x]) \\ x_1x_4 \\ x_2x_4 \\ x_3x_4 \\ \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}}(1 - 4x_4^2) \end{bmatrix}.$$

4. Tangential Components

Statistical inference from 3D projective shape data is often based upon tangential components. The tangential components for the VW embedded data is given in Patrangenaru and Ellingson (2015). Let $Y_a = \iota_{\mathbb{R}P^3}(X_a)$, with $a = 1, \dots, n$ then since sample mean \bar{Y} ;

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \iota_{\mathbb{R}P^3}(X_i)$$

lies in the ambient space it converges almost surely to mean $\tilde{\mu} = E[\iota_{\mathbb{R}P^3}(X_1)]$, the expectation of the embedded $\mathbb{R}P^3$ random variable. Let P be the projection map from \mathbb{R}^9 to $\iota_{\mathbb{R}P^3}(\mathbb{R}P^3)$. Random vector $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$ has a degenerate covariance matrix. Denote the tangential component of differential random vector $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$ as $\tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$

Now we have that as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sqrt{n} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}) \xrightarrow{d} N_3(0, \tilde{\Sigma})$$

where

$$\tilde{\Sigma} = Cov\{\tan DP_{\mu}(Y_1 - \tilde{\mu})\}$$

is the covariance of the tangential component of the differential map for a single random observation.

Statistical tests are based on asymptotic chi-square statistics generated from tangential components; Patrangenaru and Ellingson (2015). In particular, under the equality of two extrinsic means in $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^q$ with independent samples

$$\sum_{j=1}^2 n_j \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y})^T \hat{\Sigma}_k^{-1} \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y}) \xrightarrow{d} \chi_{3q}^2$$

where $\hat{\Sigma}_k$ is the sample covariance of concatenated tangential components.

5. Homogeneity Testing

Guo et al. (2023) define the Extrinsic Energy Statistic for homogeneity for the two probability distributions on object space \mathcal{M} as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{j,n_1,n_2} &= \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{m=1}^{n_1} \|j(X_i) - j(Y_m)\| \\ &\quad - \frac{n_2}{nn_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{h=1}^{n_1} \|j(X_i) - j(X_h)\| \\ &\quad - \frac{n_1}{nn_2} \sum_{l=1}^{n_2} \sum_{m=1}^{n_2} \|j(Y_l) - j(Y_m)\| \end{aligned}$$

for embedding j .

When an object space possesses a tangent space one can perform the homogeneity test using tangential components. Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) note that in the case of tangential components X one should use as inputs

$$Y = X (X^T X)^{-1/2}$$

where j in the inclusion map (embedding).

6. An Application and A Monte Carlo Study

6.1 Application: AFLW2000 Data

Consider the AFLW2000 3D landmark dataset from Zhu et al. (2016). This dataset consists of 2000 images that have been annotated with image-level 68-point 3D facial landmarks;

This data set is routinely used in the computer vision literature for the evaluation of 3D facial landmark detection models. In our application we worked with 11 landmarks; 9, 31, 32, 34, 36, 37, 46, 49, 52, 55 and 58. Projective frame was the first 5 landmarks from which we generated our projective coordinates in $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^6$. Here we chose two groups each with the landmarks of 30 images. In the first group the people were nearly facing forward like in a driver's license photo;

In the second group they were not forward facing but exhibited a rotation of less than 45 degrees;

We found that the VW, Nash and $\text{vech}(\text{VW})$ embedding-based mean test statistics had observed values 26.431, 26.431 and 26.240 with an asymptotic cutoff of $\chi_{18,0.95}^2 = 28.8693$. The lack of significance for the mean tests is probably due to the small sample size and the high dimensionality of the data lying in $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^6$.

The results for our various homogeneity tests are shown in the table below.

P-values				
	VW	VW _{tan}	Nash	Nash _{tan}
MRPP	0.0009	0.0001	0.0012	0.0001
EE-test	0.0009	0.0001	0.0008	0.0001

Here we see that the embedded data procedures concluded that there a statistically significant difference in the frontal view and side view distributions. The high significance of each of the homogeneity tests is probably because the landmarks for the modest view images are more difficult to estimate than those for the frontal views. Furthermore, tests based upon tangential components have the highest significance. This is most likely because tangential components represent a first-order linear approximation of data lying on manifold $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^q$.

Next, we consider classification error rates from the SVM algorithm using (i) embedded data and (ii) tangential component data. Here a radial kernel is used and the table of classification error rates for these various procedures.

Classification Error Rates			
VW	VW _{tan}	Nash	Nash _{tan}
Not applicable	0.017	0.000	0.017

Here we see that the SVM procedures based on tangential components have misclassification error rate that are generally no larger than those of the embedded SVM procedures, as one would expect.

6.2 Simulated Power Values for Synthetic Anatomical Landmark Data

Here we consider a Monte Carlo study involved simulated anatomical landmark data. The origin of this simulated data is the macaque data. This data set consists of random samples of 9 male and 9 female skulls from which 3D coordinates are recorded for seven anatomical landmarks. The full Procrustes mean shapes for the males and females are computed in Dryden and Mardia (2016). Below is a three-dimensional graph of these mean shapes

generated in the shapes R package where the mean male landmark points are shown in red and mean female landmark points are shown in blue.

Here the minimum of the seven Euclidean distances between the mean landmark points was 1.984. Our Monte Carlo study simulates from the two populations generated by the randomly perturbing the 7 anatomical landmarks for the average male and female macaques. For each simulation run these perturbations were trivariate and independent uniform realizations over the interval $(-1, 1)$. With each simulated data set, we consider the statistical tests and procedures from the previous section.

In our Monte Carlo study we had 1,000 runs in which independent samples of size 150 for each set of gender landmarks was performed. We took the first five landmark points to be our projective frame from which we generated our projective coordinates in $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^2$.

For the VW and Nash embedding-based mean test statistics the table below gives the simulated power values for each of these three tests

Statistical Power	
VW	Nash
0.350(0.052)	0.348(0.051)

The table below gives the simulated power values for each of the eight homogeneity testing procedures, with significance levels are shown in parentheses.

Statistical Power				
	VW	VW _{tan}	Nash	Nash _{tan}
MRPP	0.314(0.054)	0.999(0.050)	0.312(0.054)	0.998(0.052)
EE-test	0.313(0.054)	0.998(0.052)	0.314(0.053)	0.998(0.051)

Here again we see that all three procedures perform comparably under the alternative hypothesis. We see that homogeneity testing with tangential component data is statistically significantly more powerful than simply using the embedded data values.

Finally, we again considered average classification error rates from the SVM algorithm using (i) embedded data and (ii) tangential component data. Here a radial kernel was again used.

Classification Error Rates			
VW	VW _{tan}	Nash	Nash _{tan}
Not applicable	0.08572	0.20677	0.08651

We see that the VW and Nash tangential component-based SVM procedures are very similar in terms of performance. However, the tangential component based procedures had significantly lower classification error rates than the singular Nash embedded-based procedure.

7. Conclusions

For 3D projective shape analysis the vector-valued Nash embedding is preferred over the matrix-valued VW embedding in data science applications since (i) It is a vector embedding and performs as well as the state of the art VW matrix embedding when this embedding can be used in a statistical procedure and (ii) It provides easy access to further analysis and visualization with traditional vector-based statistical techniques.

We found that homogeneity testing with tangential component data is more powerful than simply using embedded data values. We found that SVM classification using tangential component data has lower classification error rates than that based on embedded data values.

8. Acknowledgements

The research in this manuscript was supported by the National Science Foundation under Grants DMS - 2311058 (Paige), DMS - 2311059 (Patrangenaru) and a Grant of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI -UEFISCDI, project number COFUND-M-ERANET-3-SMILE, within PNCDI III (Pricop-Jeckstadt).

REFERENCES

- Algahtani, A. (2023). Limit Theorems for Object Data with Applications to 2D and 3D Image Data Analysis. PhD Dissertation, Florida State University.
- Dryden, L. and Mardia, K.V. (2016). *Statistical Shape Analysis: With Applications in R*, 2nd Edition, Wiley.
- Guo, R., Lee, H. and Patrangenaru, V. (2023). Test for Homogeneity of Random Objects on Manifolds with Applications to Biological Shape Analysis. *Sankhya A* 85, 1178-1204.
- Hartley, R., Gupta, R. and Chang, T. (1992), Stereo from uncalibrated cameras, *Proceedings, IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 761-764.
- Hendriks, H. (1990). Nonparametric Estimation of a Probability Density on Riemannian Manifold Using Fourier Expansions. *Annals of Statistics*, 18, 832-849.
- Kukreja, S, Kumar, T., Bharate, V., Purohit, A., Dasgupta, A. and Guha, D. (2023). Vector Databases and Vector Embeddings-Review, *International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Image Processing (IWAIP)*, Yogyakarta, Indonesia, 231-236.
- Ma, Y., Soatto, S., Kosecka, J. and Sastry, S.S. (2006). *An Invitation to 3-D Vision*, Springer, New York.
- Mardia, K.V. and Patrangenaru, V. (2005). Directions and Projective Shapes. *Annals of Statistics*, 33, 1666-1699.
- Nash, John (1956). The imbedding problem for Riemannian manifolds. *Annals of Mathematics. Second Series*. 63 (1): 20–63.
- Paige, R.L. and Patrangenaru, V. (2024). Infimum Dimension Nash Embeddings for 2D Projective Shape, *Annals of Data Science* (submitted)
- Patrangenaru, V. and Ellingson, L. (2015). *Nonparametric Statistics on Manifolds and their Applications to Object Data Analysis*, CRC Press, Florida.
- Tirao, J. and Zurr, I. (2014). Spherical Functions: The Spheres vs. The Projective Spaces, *Journal of Lie Theory*, 24, 147-157.
- Zhu, X., Lei, Z., Liu, X., Shi, H. and Li, S.Z. (2016). Face Alignment Across Large Poses: A 3D Solution, *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 146-155.